

Supplementary material for:

Evaluating the reliability of tree-ring-based estimates of aboveground biomass and biomass increment in managed forests

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Figure S1. Frequency density of (A) normalized age of trees sampled in the dendroecological plots where each line represents one plot and (B) DBH distributions for dendroecological plots and inventory plots at the last inventory available. Normalized age was estimated as the difference between the age of each tree in each plot and the mean age of trees in each plot.

Figure S2. DBH distribution per species for live and extracted trees in all permanent and inventories. Extracted trees were mostly harvested, but also dead trees from natural causes. Cause of death or extraction from the plot was not recorded in permanent plots.

A Allometric equations for bark with DBH over bark

B Allometric equations for bark with DBH under bark

Figure S3. Relationships between bark thickness and A) diameter at breast height over bark (DBH_{over bark} in cm) and B) diameter at breast height under bark (DBH_{under bark} in cm) developed with measurements from trees sampled in dendroecological plots. Equations show linear relationships and correlation statistics for each species.

Inventory-to-sampling intervals

Figure S4. Inventory-to-sampling intervals was defined as the time interval between the dates of each periodic inventory of each permanent plot (between 1963 to 2016) and the time of sampling of dendroecological plots (2016, 2019 or 2020). The figure shows examples for three *P. sylvestris* plots.

Figure S5. Mean species tree-ring derived above ground biomass increment (AGBi) for the four species analyzed for the full time span available for each plot. Color lines represent plot-level AGBi values, and black thick lines represent species means. Grey shade shows the inventory period for each species.

Figure S6. Relationship between: (1) AGBi estimated from permanent plots and differences between AGBi from dendroecological plots, and (2) AGBi estimated from permanent plots, in a) shown in absolute terms and b) in relative terms (%). Figure shows that, in general, differences are larger in both cases for more productive sites or faster growing plots.

Figure S7. Contrasted examples of above ground biomass increment (AGBi) derived from repeated inventories (black lines) and from dendroecological plots (color lines and dots) for two plots per species at the dates of forest inventories. To compare plots of equal size, thick black lines represent the mean from 1000 randomizations of all trees present at the time considered for an equal number of trees as those sampled for tree rings. Error bars are one standard deviation around the mean from those randomized draws. Note different y-scales for each species.